

A SYSTEMIC REVIEW ON MICRO NEEDLE DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

The most widely used methods for transdermal administration of the drugs are hypodermic needles, topical creams, and transdermal patches. The effect of most of the therapeutic agents is limited due to the stratum corneum layer of the skin, which serves as a barrier for the molecules and thus only a few molecules are able to reach the site of action. A new form of delivery system called the microneedles helps to enhance the delivery of the drug through this route and overcoming the various problems associated with the conventional formulations. For instance, drug loading method, stability of drugs, and retention time are subjects of debate. Besides, the application of novel refining fabrication methods, types of materials, and instruments are other

issues that need further attention. Herein, we tried to summarize recent achievements in controllable drug delivery systems (microneedle patches) in vitro and in vivo settings. In addition, we discussed the influence of delivered drugs on the cellular mechanism and immunization molecular signaling pathways through the intradermal delivery route. Understanding the putative efficiency of microneedle patches in human medicine can help us develop and design sophisticated therapeutic modalities.

KEYWORDS: Micro needle, stability, in vitro, in vivo, patches.

INTRODUCTION

During the last decades, numerous attempts have been made to deliver recommended dose of drugs and therapeutic compounds to the target tissues with fewer side effects. Due to ease of access and less invasive manipulation, transdermal delivery of target molecules has been at the center of attention. This approach is a newly generated delivery route system that solves

previous disadvantages such as pain, patient anxiety, low dose delivery, and other side effects. Besides, the transdermal delivery route has diminished the possible biodegradation of drugs inside the gastrointestinal tract and through hepatic activity. Despite these advantages, cutaneous tissue develops a substantial barrier against multiple foreign agents with specific physicochemical properties. The epidermal layer is the first target surface for the transdermal delivery route to release the target compound into the blood circulation. It was suggested that lipophilic compounds with low molecular weight (<500 Da) can easily cross the epidermal layer; however, it is difficult for pharmaceutical bio-macromolecules and other biomolecules such as nucleic acids or proteins, to reach deeper layer of skin. In line with this claim, both passive and active methods have been applied to increase transdermal delivery of target compounds. In the passive methods, optimized drug formulation or application of carriers often leads to restricted transfer of bio-macromolecules.^[1] By contrast, the application of active physical or mechanical modalities yields outstanding skin permeability, even for compounds with higher molecular weights. For instance, several microneedles (MN) with different needle lengths (from 100 to 1100 μm) and needle densities per cm^2 have been fabricated for different purposes. Of note, the local application of MN containing needle in 100–700 μm length can generate micro-sized channels through the stratum corneum, leading to facilitated delivery of target molecules to the target sites. Based on histological studies, the average thickness of the stratum corneum is about 10 μm . It should not be forgotten the fact that the chemical properties of certain drugs can be affected using direct conventional transdermal administration which per se restricts further absorption through the subcutaneous layer into the systemic circulation. Development of sophisticated delivery systems such as MN not only can increase the delivery efficiently but also reduce the total dose of medication. Some features such as the dissolving rate of needles can also vary bioavailability rate. As a correlate, modification of needle geometry and size can help us to increase the deeper transdermal release of drugs. Besides, the application of water-soluble formulations or localization of biopharmaceutical agents juxtaposed to needle tips way from the basement could also stimulate drug bioavailability. Besides, different geometrical values such as needle side wall thickness, needle height, and tip radii, as well as aspect ratio are identical in the fabrication and delivery of various compounds into the deeper layer of cutaneous tissue.

A higher aspect ratio (needle height/width ratio) can result in the development of painless MN during insertion into the cutaneous tissue while an excessive aspect ratio diminishes mechanical strength. Because of the direct application of transdermal patches, other issues

such as mechanical rigidity, loading capacity of needles, responsiveness to external stimuli, and low probability of pain should be considered.

To date, several physical penetration enhancers such as MN, iontophoresis, electroporation, sonophoresis, ablative laser microporation, and chemical penetration enhancers like fatty acids, alcohols, esters, etc. have been used to increase delivery efficiency through the transdermal route. The chemical penetration enhancers are easy to be produced in various chemical structures and are applicable without additive tools and professional clinicians. However, the chemical penetration approach may enhance the risk of severe skin inflammation especially when hydrophilic molecules are used for accelerating the delivery of therapeutic molecules. In contrast, the physical penetration enhancers provide a less invasive platform for fast and adjustable dose drug delivery. Among them, the iontophoresis method is based on voltage gradient delivery of therapeutic agent through stratum corneum, the outer layer of the epidermis, by creating nano-sized holes. It has been suggested that this approach is more appropriate for the delivery of lipophilic and small size molecules. The efficiency of iontophoresis-based delivery is associated with the loaded drug concentration, pH of drug solution, ionic component, and physicochemical conditions. In the sonophoresis method, ultrasound waves are exploited to improve skin permeability by increasing the local temperature and applying mechanical longitudinal force for transdermal delivery. Although sonophoresis is known to be safe, cheap, and functional, the heating effects can alter the therapeutic effects of thermal-sensitive molecules during transdermal delivery. However, sonophoresis also stimulates skin permeability via non-thermal approaches by tethering generated microbubble through ultrasound waves. Electroporation supports transdermal delivery using high-voltage electric pulses based on membrane rearrangement and pore formation. Ideally, the electroporation pulses can also induce an immune response within transdermal delivery (notably through vaccine delivery). However, the unprogrammed number of pulses and treatment elongation may cause severe damage to keratinocyte and resident cells. In ablative laser microporation, skin resurfacing is done by laser irradiation which facilitates topical absorption and further systemic delivery to remote sites. Similar to the other physical penetration enhancers, ablative laser facilitates the transdermal delivery of high molecular weight and hydrophilic molecules. The drug absorption can be interrupted if laser irradiation forms a large-scale coagulation area in the damaged tissue around microchannels.

Recently, MN devices equipped with an array of needles with a size of less than 500 μm have been developed for efficient delivery through an epidermal barrier (Figure). One of the most prominent advantages of the MN system would be that both small- and large-sized molecules such as nucleic acids, proteins, vaccines, hormones, nanoparticles, and virus-like particles can be loaded in MN devices. MN devices enhance patient compliance because of painless injections while preventing in situ infections caused by conventional needles. However, the development of novel micro-fabrication methods and stability drugs inside the MN devices are still challenging. Even though the MN system has excellent potential to be an alternative to traditional methods, it can contribute to skin irritation or allergic reactions. Progress in the development of MN devices has increased hopes for using less specialized personnel worldwide by creating self-health administration opportunities.

Available approached purposed for transdermal delivery using MN patch system.

Description	Topical cream	Transdermal patch	Hypodermic needle	Microneedle
Description	Emulsion/ emulgel/ cream/ ointments	Adhesive patch to be placed on the skin	Fine, hollow tube having a sharp tip with small opening at the end	Micron size needles are aligned on the surface of a small patch
Onset of action	Slow	Slow	Faster	Faster
Pain	Painless	Painless	Painful	Painless
Bioavailability	Poor	Insufficient	Sufficient	Sufficient
Patient compliance	Less	Better	Less	Better
Self-	Possible	Possible	Not possible	Possible

administration				
Mechanism of drug delivery	Permeation through skin pores.	Drug has to cross stratum corneum barrier, thus poor diffusion of large molecules	Drug placed directly in the dermis	Bypass stratum corneum and drug placed directly into epidermis or dermis hence enhanced permeability

Comparison between topical cream, transdermal patch, hypodermic needle, and microneedle drug delivery systems.

Comparison of topical cream, hypodermic needle, microneedle patch and transdermal patch.

Mechanism of drug delivery

The delivery of the drug through the topical route follows the diffusion mechanism. In the microneedle drug delivery system, the skin is temporarily disrupted. A microneedle device is made by arranging hundreds of microneedles in arrays on a tiny patch (the same as that of a normal transdermal patch available in the market) in order to deliver sufficient amount of drug to give a required therapeutic response. It pierces the stratum corneum thus bypassing the barrier layer. The drug is directly placed in the epidermis or upper dermis layer which then goes into the systemic circulation and shows a therapeutic response on reaching the site of action. Mechanism of drug delivery through microneedles is depicted in Figure.

Dimensions of microneedles

Microneedles can be formulated in varying sizes depending on the type of microneedle and the material used. Since the epidermis is up to 1500 μm thick so the needle length of up to 1500 μm is sufficient to release the drug into the epidermis. Needles larger in length and thicker in diameter can go deep into the dermis, damage the nerves and cause pain. Mostly they are 150–1500 microns long, 50–250 microns wide, and have 1–25 microns tip thickness. As discussed earlier the need for microneedle device is to create micron size transport

pathway, the diameter of needles is kept between few microns. Microneedle tips can be cylindrical, triangular, pointed, pentagonal, octagonal and are available in many more shapes.

Fig. Mechanism of drug delivery by microneedle device: (1) Microneedle device with drug solution; (2) Device inserted into the skin; (3) Temporary mechanical disruption of the skin; (4) Releasing the drug in the epidermis; (5) Transport of drug to the site of action.

Microneedle fabrication material and its properties

1. Silicon

The first microneedle was made from silicon in the 1990s. Silicon is anisotropic in nature and has a crystalline structure. Its properties depend on the alignment in the crystal lattice, which shows different elastic moduli (50 to 180 GPa). Its flexible nature allows producing needles of different sizes and shapes. Its attractive physical properties make it a versatile material. Silicon substrates can be precisely manufactured and are capable of batch production. The cost of silicon and its time-consuming complex fabrication process limits its use in microneedle. In addition, there are some biocompatibility issues, as silicon is brittle, some part may break and remain in the skin thus causing some health issues.

2. Metal

The main metals used are stainless-steel and titanium. Palladium, nickel, palladium-cobalt alloys are also used. They have good mechanical properties and good biocompatibility. Metals are strong enough to avoid breaking, thus more suitable as compared to silicon for microneedle production. The first metal used in the production of microneedle was stainless steel. Titanium is a good alternative to stainless steel.

3. Ceramic

Alumina (Al_2O_3) is mainly used because of its chemical resistance. It forms a stable oxide because of the highly energetic ionic and covalent bonds between Al and O atoms. Other

types of ceramics used are calcium sulfate dihydrate [Gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 0.2\text{H}_2\text{O}$)] and calcium phosphate dihydrate [Brushite ($\text{CaHPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$)]. In recent years an organically modified ceramic called Ormocer® has been used. It is a three-dimensionally cross-linked copolymer. A polymer with different properties can be produced by using different organic units during polymerization. Mainly they are produced using a micromolding technique. Ceramic slurry is cast into a micro-mold. Micro moulding techniques are cheaper processes, and also have the potential for scale-up.

4. Silica glass

Varying geometries can be produced on small scale using glass. Silica glass is physiologically inert but brittle in nature. Borosilicate glass which is made up of silica and boron trioxide is more elastic. They are mostly fabricated manually, thus are less time efficient. Glass MNs are not used now commercially, but only for experimental purposes.

5. Carbohydrate

Maltose is one of the most common sugars used. Other sugars, such as mannitol, trehalose, sucrose, xylitol and galactose, polysaccharides can also be used. Carbohydrate slurries are moulded by making use of silicon or metal templates. The drug-loaded carbohydrate mixture is casted into the moulds to get the microneedles. The time-based dissolution of carbohydrate regulates the drug release inside the skin. Carbohydrates are cheap and safe for the human health but degradation at high temperatures makes the fabrication process difficult.

6. Polymer

A wide variety of polymers including poly (methyl methacrylate) (PMMA), polylactic acid (PLA), poly (lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA), polyglycolic acid (PGA), poly (carbonate), cyclic-olefin copolymer, poly (vinylpyrrolidone) (PVP), poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVA), polystyrene (PS), poly (methyl vinyl ether-comaleic anhydride), SU-8 photoresist are reported for microneedles preparation. Mostly, dissolving or biodegradable and hydrogel forming microneedles arrays are made from these polymers. Microneedles fabricated with these polymers have less strength than other materials but are tougher than glass and ceramics.

Different Manufacturing Strategies

Multiple methodologies exist for the production of microneedles using several materials. Microneedles can be fabricated either by using a mold or by direct manufacturing methods to meet the demands of large-scale production.

1. Microelectromechanical System (MEMS)

This technique fabricates hollow and solid microneedles and prepares molds for dissolving microneedles (Figure). It involves three processes, namely deposition, patterning, and etching. During the deposition process, a thin layer of material, typically ranging from nanometer to micrometer thickness, is deposited through physical or chemical vapor deposition. During the patterning process, the two-dimensional pattern of the material from the mask is transferred onto the substrate coated with photoresist. Ultimately, the patterned substrate undergoes etching through the utilization of etchants. The undesirable material is eliminated from the surface of the substrate, resulting in the fabrication of the final functional microneedle. There are two recognized types of etching processes: dry and wet etching. Wet etching involves removing undesired material by submerging it in a liquid etchant. The isotropic approach involves the etchant uniformly corroding the material from all directions simultaneously. These etchants corrode various materials, including oxides, nitrides, gold, silicon, aluminum, and others. Anisotropic etchants selectively corrode materials at varying speeds and in different orientations. Anisotropic etchants are employed to process silicon wafers and produce precisely regulated geometries. Dry etching is a process that treats materials using inert or reactive gases at low temperatures.

Figure a) Fabrication of microneedle array by photolithography combined with deep reactive ion etching. (b) Laser ablation: (i) CO₂ laser cutting for acrylic mold fabrication by crossover lines (COL) technique and (ii) PDMS mold fabrication using acrylic mold. (c) Microneedles via direct ink drawing. (d) 3D-printed microneedles.

2. Micromolding

Micromolding is the predominant method employed for the production of microneedles. The process entails using a negative mold containing hollow spaces for loading material. Subsequently, the material undergoes a cooling and curing process, followed by the removal

of the mold. This approach can be used to process materials such as polymers, hydrogels, and ceramics. Various curing and shape-forming techniques are employed depending on the characteristics of the materials. This technique has benefits such as being easily replicated, straightforward, and cost-effective. This technology allows for the step-by-step input of loads and materials into the microneedles and composites. Different mold-filling methods, such as centrifugation, vacuum, infiltration, spin coating, imprinting, atomized spray, etc., are employed to address the challenges associated with filling the mold cavities. Demolding hydrogels poses a challenge due to the potential risk of damaging the microneedles. This approach cannot produce intricate structures, such as hollow structures and structures with barbs. Furthermore, this technology cannot process materials such as metals, glass, and silicone.

3. Injection Molding

Injection molding is a cost-effective and often employed technique for the large-scale manufacturing of microneedles. The injection machine introduces a blend of polymer and metal into the cavities of the mold. Injection molding offers exceptional consistency, precise metering, and enhanced injection flow rates. The approach is plagued by the disadvantages of expensive equipment, challenging control over small shot size, and labor-intensive nature. This technique enables the production of microneedles on flexible surfaces by solidifying liquid ingredients on a mold. Yu et al. investigated how different processing parameters impact the filling fraction of a microneedle array made of polylactic acid. The filling fraction of microneedles increased with higher packing pressure.

4. Laser Cutting

The manufacture of metal microneedles involves using 3D laser cutting and laser ablation techniques, which are employed with either positive or negative molds. Laser cutting is the process of using an infrared laser and computer-aided design software to create solid microneedle arrays. This technique can successfully attain the intended form, structure, and size of microneedles. This approach is advantageous since it allows for the fabrication of two-dimensional arrays of metallic microneedles as well as a single array of microneedles with different geometries. Anbazhagan et al. fabricated a solid polymer microneedle patch made of PDMS utilizing a CO₂ laser and molding technique. Two-needle geometries, specifically conical and pyramidal shapes, were manufactured using laser cutting techniques. This integrated approach is well-suited for the high-volume manufacturing of microneedles.

Laser ablation involves the formation of solid metal arrays through the use of light pulses that cause a particular shape to protrude on a metal plate. If the laser radiation is sufficiently intense, continuous-wave lasers can also be employed for material bulging. Laser ablation can be applied to any metal to achieve the desired shape. This technique is particularly advantageous for the rapid production of microneedles. Nevertheless, the temperature impact resulting from the radiation can create issues in the composition and mechanical integrity of the manufactured microneedles. Additionally, it can result in the formation of cracks and reduced fatigue resistance in the produced microneedles. This approach could be better for the large-scale manufacturing of microneedles, and the equipment utilized may be more cost-effective. An alternative method for fabricating microneedles with a high aspect ratio, without the necessity for a cleanroom, has been reported (Figure). An acrylic mold was used to build the microneedles, while CO₂ laser cutting equipment was employed to produce conical microneedles.

5. Drawing Lithography

Lithographic drawing is a method that produces microneedles measuring in millimeters in height. This method employs the glass transition temperature of polymeric materials for producing microneedles (as shown in Figure). The glass transition refers to the dynamic transformation of the amorphous portion of a polymer material from a solid to a liquid state. Through the manipulation of 2D viscous polymer materials, microneedles are formed using drawing techniques to create 3D structures. These microneedles are then exposed to various forces such as gravity, centrifugal force, thermal field, magnetic field, and electric field, which take advantage of the material's properties. The drawing lithography process uses the tensile and elongating capabilities of viscous fluids. The process involves the interaction and elongation of polymer droplets with high viscosity, resulting in the formation of microneedle structures. The produced microneedles will exhibit low mechanical strength and lack the ability to adjust their shape precisely.

6. 3D Printing-Based Techniques

Using 3D printing techniques, it is possible to develop microneedles with intricate 3D structures (Figure). It encompasses many techniques such as stereolithography (SLA), two-photon polymerization (TPP), liquid crystal display (LCD), projection-based printing (PBP), continuous liquid interface production (CLIP), selected laser sintering (SLS), selected laser

melting (SLM), and others. The fabrication of metal microneedles involves the employment of two methods: selected laser sintering and selected laser melting.

Stereolithography is the predominant technique employed for fabricating microneedles, owing to its exceptional precision and high-resolution capabilities, resulting in superior surface quality. The process utilizes a photopolymerization approach, where laser radiation is used to illuminate a liquid photopolymer resin and trigger a polymerization reaction. Subsequently, the microneedles undergo a thorough cleansing in an alcohol solution to eliminate any remaining unreacted resin. They are then exposed to ultraviolet (UV) light for curing, resulting in the production of the ultimate microneedle arrays. Nevertheless, the approach is laborious, expensive, and has a restricted selection of printable materials. Tang et al. investigated the influence of various 3D-printing parameters on the efficacy of the transdermal drug delivery method. The study was conducted to investigate the impact of temperature, extrusion width, nozzle orifice diameter, infill width, and layer thickness on the fabrication of milliprojections using poly(lactic acid). The print's surface smoothness was improved by reducing the nozzle diameter and increasing the spacing between the milliprojections while maintaining the same level of precision. 3D bioprinted microneedles have grabbed the attention of researchers due to their increased permeation, efficacy, and safety. 3D-printed microneedles have been used in regenerative medicine and tissue engineering applications to deliver viable cell cargo. These microneedles can safeguard the bioactive agent and help in controlled delivery.

CONCLUSION

The effectiveness of drug administration using microneedle patches mostly relies on successful penetration of the epidermal barrier. In recent decades, significant studies have been dedicated to creating and developing microneedle patches to deliver drugs and monitor different biomarkers within the body. The field of biomedical research has seen a surge of interest in developing and producing a medication release mechanism that can be activated or regulated as needed. This article provides an overview of the many methods used to create microneedles, the various types of microneedles, and the materials utilized in their fabrication, specifically focusing on their applications in biomedicine. The improvements in microneedle-based controlled release systems across several areas are potentially revolutionizing medicine delivery and various disease detection and monitoring systems.

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